

PROBLEMS OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT AS A MEANS OF COMMUNICATION IN THE ERA OF GLOBAL DIGITALIZATION

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The world is rapidly moving online, “digitally”. The digital environment is the technological basis for all actions taken by a person in the online space. A number is a marker of time, a tool that has a comprehensive effect and is used by everyone. The number is present in all significant aspects of a person’s life and changes his role in relation to both the events and facts of the current time, and to the process of world development.

Every day brings us new challenges and non-standard tasks. Modern technologies erase boundaries and change culture. Digital studies are, first of all, studies of the changing experience of humanity. Thomas Friedman once said: “The world will care less and less about what knowledge you have, because everything can be found on Google. What’s more important is what you do with your knowledge later.”

The digital environment has led to the emergence of a special type of text, with a special type of author and a specific modality of communication in the field of mass communications - media text. Digitalization is erasing the differences between media and, accordingly, types of media content. The world's largest companies are moving to create digital ecosystems. The digital world of a particular person is becoming more and more personalized. Communication today is “imposed” at all possible points of contact - in order to attract, interest and retain the consumer, to force him or her to “join the community” and not to destroy his or her trust [1].

Digital technologies are transforming communication and social systems, changing the structure of information consumption: unification and clipping of texts is becoming a natural trend, taking into account the simplified needs of the audience.

Digital reality is becoming an actor in a new round of cultural development. Experts argue that modern humanity already lives in a mental infrastructure created by social networks and technologies for the formation of consciousness that exceed the capabilities of human mental activity.

The word is one of the main structural units of language, which serves to name objects, their qualities and characteristics, their interactions, as well as to name imaginary and abstract concepts created by the human imagination. The word is a building material for expressing thoughts. Only man has the unique opportunity to put his or her thoughts into words. Cyberspace leads to the “dying of thoughts,” to the loss of diversity, nonlinearity of existence and “forced” linearization [2].

In the modern world, digital technologies play an important role in human life and are increasingly being introduced into various spheres of society, including the linguistic one. With the development of Internet technologies, mobile devices and social networks, there is an active penetration of digital tools into the field of language and communication. In this regard, the study of the Russian language in the context of digital transformation becomes especially relevant and important for understanding the processes occurring with the language in modern conditions.

Digital transformation has a significant impact on the teaching and learning of the Russian language, on its use in the Internet environment and on the general language culture. Therefore, it is important to study this process in order to identify possible problems and determine the prospects for the development of the Russian language in the era of digitalization. The Russian language is actively adapting to the specifics of Internet communication: abbreviations, acronyms, emoticons and memes appear. These new forms enrich the language, but can be difficult to understand for those unfamiliar with the context in which they are used [3].

The development of digital technologies has a significant impact on the educational environment, including the process of learning languages such as Russian. In this context, electronic textbooks, online courses, mobile applications and other digital tools are becoming increasingly popular among teachers and students.

Electronic textbooks: Electronic textbooks facilitate access to materials for studying the Russian language, allowing students and teachers to obtain information from various sources. They can also contain multimedia elements such as audio, video and interactive exercises, making learning more interesting and effective.

Online courses: Online courses in the Russian language provide the opportunity to study at a time convenient for the student, overcoming geographical and time restrictions. Courses may include video lectures, online tests, and forums for student communication and collaboration. This format of training allows us to use an individual approach to each student and take into account his level of knowledge and speed of learning.

Mobile apps: Mobile apps for learning Russian are available on different platforms and provide a wide range of features such as dictionaries, phrase books, audio and video materials, and interactive exercises. These apps allow students to study anytime and anywhere, which increases their motivation and speeds up their learning process.

The Russian language is actively integrated into various digital educational platforms, which makes it possible for foreign students to study it and promotes intercultural exchange. The integration of the Russian language into international educational platforms also helps to promote Russian culture and history at the global level, which increases interest in learning this language. Virtual Language Labs and Educational Games: Virtual language labs and educational games in Russian help students develop speaking, writing, reading and listening skills in an interactive and fun environment. Such tools can be used either independently or as a supplement to classical training [4].

Digital transformation has a significant impact on the Russian language and its development. On the one hand, this creates new opportunities for the use of language and the dissemination of information. On the other hand, it also leads to new problems such as spelling and grammatical errors, the use of colloquial forms and slang in texts. To preserve and develop the Russian language in the electronic environment, it is necessary to conduct various campaigns aimed at promoting literacy and attention to the rules of the Russian language.

The potential of the Russian language in the architecture of global postmodernity is determined by and largely depends on the success of its adaptation and development in the conditions of the growing dynamics of the cultural process. From this point of view, two main problems acquire particular relevance: firstly, maintaining the status of the Russian language as an aggregator of national spiritual culture as a whole and, secondly, strengthening its position in enhancing Russian or Russian traditional values [5].

It is also important to raise awareness about the problem of spelling and grammatical errors and actively discuss this topic in society. In this article, we would like to offer practical recommendations for the preservation and development of the Russian language in the electronic environment, such as the use of virtual language laboratories and educational games in Russian to develop speaking, writing, reading and listening skills in an interactive and entertaining environment[6].

In general, we would like to emphasize the need to study constantly the process of digital transformation to identify possible problems and determine the prospects for the development of the Russian language in the era of digitalization. It is important to consider the opinions and needs of language users when developing new technologies and applications. It is important to create tools that help users improve their speaking, writing, reading and listening skills in Russian.

As a result of the study, the Russian language, as one of the most widespread languages in the world, due to its natural qualities, has a high adaptive potential in the current global sociocultural reality, which involves the formation of an open

information space in which all the languages of small and large nations and states are speech carriers of unique cultural values not only preserve, but also acquire new, unique content. The process of forming future cultural diversity cannot be built with the help of any cultural determinant, but can only be promoted on the basis of complementary interaction of all subjects of the global cultural landscape.

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